

**ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ИПОТЕЧНОГО КРЕДИТОВАНИЯ
В ЭКОНОМИКЕ**

Ozatbekova Ozodakhon

Student of the faculty of economics,
e-mail: ozoda.ozatbekova@mail.ru

Ozatbekov Yusupkhon

Assistant of the department of transport economics
e-mail: yusuf.ozodbekov@mail.ru

Gulamov Abdulaziz Abdullayevich

Vice-rector for academic affairs of
Tashkent State University of transport
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Abstract: This thesis talks about the historical origin of mortgage loans issued to commercial banks belonging to the financial services sector of the economy, mainly for housing repairs of social strata, and about the economic and social significance of mortgage loans in foreign countries.

Keywords: macro economic indicators, mortgage loan, profitability, soft loan, mechanism, secondary market, alternative financing, institutional system.

Mortgage lending is a market instrument for the circulation of property rights to real estate in cases where purchase and sale, other forms of treatment are inappropriate from a legal or commercial point of view, which allows you to attract additional funds for the implementation of various projects. Those who are faced with a mortgage for the first time have the impression that a mortgage is heavy, time-consuming and expensive. However, a mortgage can be the easiest and fastest way to improve your living conditions if you carefully consider the choice of a loan program, learn about possible benefits, choose a convenient way to repay the loan and correctly assess future expenses. The mortgage provides the mortgagee with repayment of the principal amount of the debt under the loan agreement or other mortgage-backed obligation in full or in part provided for by the mortgage agreement.

The term mortgage first appeared in Greece in the sixth century BC. and they were connected with the provision by certain landowners of the debtor's liability to the creditor. The borrower took money from the lender (mortgage lender) and was obliged to install a special sign (pillar or stone) on the place burdened with the mortgage. This sign announced that this place was secured, a mortgage had been obtained for it.

The mortgage institution has gone through an evolutionary path from fiduciary in a relatively short time (from Lat.fiducia - a trust transaction, a transaction based on trust) to a more progressive stage - pgnus (from Latin pignus -

informal collateral), and later - mortgages. By proxy, the pledged thing becomes the property of the creditor, who, after the execution of the contract, would have the right to return the property to the debtor or sell it, refusing to demand money.

Pigna's contract provided for the transfer of real estate not to his ownership, but to his ownership as a guarantee of a loan obligation. The creditor had no right to retain the collateral and could sell the property only if the debtor, having failed to fulfill its obligations, reimbursed the borrower the difference between the sale price of this collateral and the balance of the debt.

In modern conditions, when the economy of most countries is characterized by an imbalance and deterioration of macroeconomic indicators, a decrease in economic activity, including due to the unfavorable external economic situation, one of the main conditions for the development of the country's economy and improving the welfare of the population is the development of housing construction, and the other is the improvement of long-term lending mechanisms.

As the experience of foreign countries shows, mortgage lending is one of the most reliable and effective ways to attract private investment in housing construction, and maintaining its development contributes to increasing the effective demand of the population. It is worth noting that more than 98% of the US population and about 70% of the EU population buy housing using various mortgage lending models.

In addition, the development of the mechanism of mortgage housing lending on a state scale allows maintaining a balance between the interests of society, which is expressed in improving housing conditions, the interest of the banking system and profitable activities, as well as the interests of the state, in the accelerated work of the construction industry and increasing the level of investment in the economy.

In addition, an important factor in the growth of demand for alternative sources of financing in this area in recent years is the decline in the volume of concessional lending to housing construction.

As long-term world experience shows, in such conditions, the development of the credit mortgage market should begin with fairly simple organizational models aimed at involving the population in the process of long-term financing of savings.

World experience shows that in countries where the bulk of investment in housing is financed by mortgage loans, the level of housing security is higher. In

this regard, it should be noted that in world practice there are various models of mortgage lending, each of which involves special lending mechanisms, institutional structure and sources of financing for mortgage lending. From the point of view of mortgage institutions operating in the country , there are 4 models of refinancing mortgage assets:

- 1) The model of universal banks;
- 2) the model of specialized deposit and credit organizations (including the system of construction funds);
- 3) the model of specialized mortgage banks;
- 4) the model of the secondary mortgage market.

Summing up, we can say that mortgage lending provided by banks, regardless of their type of activity, combined with housing provision for a developing young stratum is one of the aspects that play an important role in maintaining and restoring economic balance in the country.

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